

Special Issue on: "Cyber Physical Systems"

<http://airccse.org/journal/sicfp18.html>

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Theme and Scope

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) are integrations of computation, networking, and physical processes. The vision of CPS faces some core challenges of multidisciplinary research, as their relevant technologies appear in diverse areas of science and engineering.

This special issue is intended to cover contributions in both the design and analysis in the field of Cyber Physical Systems. The special issue will additionally select high quality papers from the International Conference on Recent Trends in Advance Computing - Cyber Physical Systems (ICRTAC-CPS), to be held in VIT Chennai, India, September 2018.

Topics of interest

Authors are solicited to contribute to this Special Issue by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to:

- Design, synthesis and verification of CPS
- Sustainability and environmental issues in CPS
- Social CPS computing
- Industrial CPS and smart manufacturing
- Applications of CPS in various domains such as smart energy systems, robotics and automation, automotive and transportation systems, smart healthcare, surveillance systems, etc
- Adaptive attack mitigation for CPS
- Authentication and access control for CPS
- Availability, recovery and auditing for CPS

- Data security and privacy for CPS
- Embedded systems security and privacy
- EV charging system security
- Urban transportation system security
- Vulnerability analysis for CPS
- Wireless sensor network security and privacy
- Big data modeling and analytics for CPS
- Cross-layer modeling and optimization for CPS
- Design automation for CPS
- Embedded system design for CPS
- Intrusion detection for CPS
- Key management in CPS
- Legacy CPS system protection
- Lightweight crypto and security
- Security and privacy in industrial control systems
- Smart grid security
- Threat modeling for CPS
- CPS fault detection and recovery
- CPS security and privacy

Notes for Prospective Authors

Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Issue. Manuscripts should be written in English and strictly follow the guideline of the Journal IJCNC. The manuscripts should be submitted to one of the guest editors by July 15, 2018 through email cpss@airccse.org

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : July 15, 2018**
- Notification : October 15, 2018
- Final manuscript due : October 30, 2018

For more details please visit: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijcnc.html>